

First Versus Second Order Differential Equations for Waves

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A wave on a string is characterized by a second order wave equation which follows from Newton's second law. The equation for a photon is also a second order wave equation which follows from Maxwell's classical electromagnetic equations. Both Newton's second law and Maxwell's equations are linked to force, but the wave moves at a constant velocity and is described by $v=f$ wavelength or $v=E/p$. This is a linear equation and constant velocity suggests no force in Newtonian mechanics. Nevertheless some kind of action/reaction or internal force seems to be associated with a wave.

In this note we suggest that either a free particle with rest mass or a classical wave (light etc) move at a constant velocity and so one should think in terms of a linear equation. Secondly, we suggest that a particle or classical wave represents force i.e. the particle is not simply the effect of a cause called an external force. Newton already stated this by stating that for every action there is an equal and opposite reaction. Thus we argue that a particle (or a wave like a photon etc) is linked directly to force and so more than constant velocity motion is described. As a result, we suggest that linear equations are needed to describe E (energy) and p (momentum), but these should convey the idea of force. Furthermore, these ideas should be linked to special relativity because p and E depend on the constant velocity frame in which they are observed.

Wave Equation

The wave equation $1/vv \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } W(x,t) = \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \text{partial } W(x,t)$ ((1)) may be derived from Newton's second law for a string tied at both ends. A small piece of string is considered with $dp/dt = m \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dy}{dt}$. The net force is $T(x+dx) \sin(\theta_{x+dx}) - T(x) \sin(\theta_x)$ where T is tension.

$\sin(\theta_{x+dx})$, however, is the slope dy/dx so (1):

$$1/vv \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} y(x,t) \text{ partial} = \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} y(x,t) \quad ((2))$$

Here v is a constant which happens to be the velocity of the wave. The wave, however, moves at a constant v so one might ask: Why should Newton's law be used to describe it? Even though the wave moves at a constant speed like a free particle subject to no force, there is force (i.e. tension of the string and action reaction in the problem). Nevertheless, given the constant velocity one might argue that a first order differential equation and not a second should be used as dp/dt is linked to $d/dt \frac{d}{dt} p$ while p only to dy/dt . This becomes more evident from the solution of ((2)) namely:

$$y(x,t) = A \sin(-Et+px) \quad ((3)) \quad \text{where } v=E/p$$

One may note that a first order equation, not linked to Newton's second law, may be used to obtain the wave solution equally well i.e.:

$$-1/v \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } y(x,t) = \frac{d}{dx} \text{partial } y(x,t) \quad ((4))$$

One may also notice that $A = -Et + px$ is a Lorentz invariant and go a step further and write: $dA/dx = p$ and $dA/dt = -E$. This, however, yields the numbers p and E . If one wishes to somehow include space and time as in ((4)) one may establish eigenvalue equations which separate x and t i.e.:

$$-i \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{and} \quad i \frac{d}{dt} \exp(-iEt) = E \exp(-iEt) \quad ((5b))$$

((5a)) and ((5b)) are quite different from the starting point of a second order wave equation, but perhaps contain the essence of the problem. For Newton's second law ((2)) one must link $dp/dt \rightarrow d/dt \text{partial } y$ and net force $\rightarrow d/dx \text{partial } y$, but for a free particle or wave there is no reason to have this link between x and t (or p and E). A velocity equation, either $E/p = v$ for a photon or classical wave or $p = Ev$ for a particle with rest mass links p and E , but constant motion in space which demonstrates some kind of "action-reaction" already exists for ((5a)) and ((5b)) which do not distinguish whether one has a particle with rest mass or no rest mass (e.g. photon). To bring in this extra piece of information i.e. $p = Ev$ or $v = E/p$ one requires a second equation which makes use of ((5a)) and ((5b)). For example, one might use ((5a)) and ((5b)) in $EE = pp + \text{momentum}$ to obtain the Klein-Gordon equation.

One may note that the solution for a photon also follows from a second order differential wave equation i.e. the wave equation ((2)) which is derived from Maxwell's electromagnetism equations. These equations use E (electric) and B magnetic fields and deal with forces. Thus both the wave on a string and the photon wave are linked to forces and fields. For the photon $E = E_0 \exp(-iEt + ipx)$ and B has a similar expression, but is perpendicular and E and B are perpendicular to the photon motion. Nevertheless, the photon moves at a constant speed (as if it were a free or nonaccelerating particle). The linear $v = E/p$ applies to it and one may again argue that first order derivatives such as ((5a)) and ((5b)) may describe its essence.

A Particle as Force

In deriving the wave equation for a string tied at both ends, one considers a small piece of string as the "effect" of a force, namely the internal tension. Thus a moving particle is simply the result of the force "directing" it. Newton, however, argued that every action has an equal and opposite reaction so we argue that a particle is like a force itself. The particle contains the ability to interact (e.g. through charge etc) and has momentum which allows for impulse reactions. Thus a particle should be thought of in the same way as a force or potential and not simply as a moving object. For the case of a photon, it moves with constant speed, yet it contains pieces of fields related to force i.e. E (electric) and B magnetic even though it does not contain a charge. In recent papers (2), the direct effects of the electric field of a photon is discussed. The photon also acts as a force as it imparts an impulse on a target e.g. a metal foil. As a result, it may not be enough to use numbers such as c or $E/p = c$, but an action-reaction description may be needed. We argue that ((5a)) and ((5b)) may be such a description. It is first order because this seems enough for a free particle.

If ((5a)) and ((5b)) represent the essence of a particle or wave acting as a force, then they should also apply to a particle with rest mass as already argued. In fact the general form ((5a)) and ((5b)) applies to both nonzero and zero rest masses and a second equation linking p and E is needed to distinguish i.e. $p=Ev$ and $E/p = v$.

If a particle is like a force, then one might think of it as a force field. In such a case, one would not follow the particle about in space and time. In such a case, it is viewed as the effect of a force. If it is a force itself, it might be described in a probabilistic way throughout all of space. This seems to be what the form $\exp(ipx)$ represents. The force is not linked to time, so there is not need to include time in the expression $\exp(ipx)$.

If a particle is a force and is described by $\exp(ipx)$ in the p - x form, then $V(x)$ a potential which interacts with a particle for example, should have the same form as well. In particular:

$$V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \quad V_k \exp(ikx) \quad ((6))$$

Why is potential instead of force used? If $\exp(ipx)$ describes a free particle, x can take any value so the particle may be anywhere. This seems to be a probabilistic scenario. In other words one does not follow the particle in time and space and so does not need to use force. Nevertheless there is average kinetic energy at each x which comes from a momentum distribution: $\text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and potential energy $V(x)$.

Special Relativity

As noted above, $-Et+px$, a Lorentz invariant, appears in the solution of the wave equation ((2)). Why should this appear in a solution to an equation created by Newton's second law when Newtonian mechanics is not based on special relativity? $-Et+px$ also appears in the solution for a photon and it is known that Maxwell's electromagnetic equations are Lorentz invariant

Special relativity deals with the viewing of E energy and p momentum from different constant velocity moving frames regardless of whether the particle has rest mass or not. We have argued that velocity for a particle with rest mass is $p=Ev$ and for a wave (photon) $v= E/p$. Thus the values of E' and p' define the velocity in different frames, but the general essence of motion which we suggest as ((5a)) and ((5b)) should remain the same. This follows from $-Et+px$ being an invariant as ((5a)) and ((5b)) follow directly from $-Et+px$ converted into eigenvalue single order differential equations.

Conclusion

The wave equation which holds for a tied string or a photon from Maxwell's electromagnetism equations is a second order differential equation and seems to be linked to forces and action-reaction. For example, Newton's second law is used to obtain the wave equation for a string and the electric and magnetic fields appear in the solution for a photon. Nevertheless, there is a constant velocity for the photon and classical wave which suggests free motion and no acceleration. One has $v=E/p$. This seems to suggest that a single derivative and a second derivative is needed. For example, $dp/dt = d/dt \partial y(x,t) / \partial t$ for a string, but p is represented by a single derivative $m \, dy/dt \partial$. Furthermore a wave (which is like a zero rest mass free

particle) represents a force as it may strike an object e.g. a foil and impart an impulse. A particle with rest mass may do the same. Thus in terms of representing a force, a free particle with or without rest mass seem to be the same. They differ in $p=Ev$ and $v=E/p$. Thus we argue that a single order differential equation should apply to each in particular to p and E separately such that one may construct $p=Ev$ (or $EE = pp + m^2c^2$) and $v=E/p$. For both zero and nonzero rest mass particles one should not simply have numbers representing E , p and v , but should represent the particle as a force i.e. having a kind of action-reaction. Finally, the form of this motion should follow from a Lorentz invariant result. We suggest $-Et + px$ and create separate first order differential equations $-i\frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$ ((5a)) and $i\frac{d}{dt} \exp(-iEt) = E \exp(-iEt)$ ((5b)) as describing the essence of either a nonzero or zero rest mass particle. The wave which suggests action-reaction shows that force is somehow included in a particle. One does not simply have translation. ((5a)) and ((5b)) may then be used in equations linking E and p which are appropriate for particles with nonzero or zero rest mass.

In the case of a potential $V(x)$, if $\exp(ipx)$ describes the particle which is a force, it should also describe the potential i.e. $V(x)=\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ exists in all of space and ((5a)) and ((5b)) separate x and t so one cannot follow the particle as it travels through x and t . Rather one has a probabilistic scenario and considers average kinetic energy of a momentum distribution $W(x)=\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and potential energy $V(x)$.

References

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